

D7.1

Facebook and YouTube Channels Initiated, Website Launched

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This document was prepared for the project GRAVITATE. It focuses on the project's dissemination and communication strategy through the internet i.e. websites and social media channels, outlining the target groups that need to be reached as well as the responsibilities of partners and a timeline for such activities.

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gravitate-project.eu

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1. Introduction

This document records the existence of the GRAVITATE project's website and social media channels. Furthermore it provides some detail on the groups targeted by the project's dissemination through these channels and summarises actions that the consortium partners are to take to consistently and effectively use the channels.

2. Target Groups

The following table summarizes the type of audience, the messages to be communicated, the impact foreseen, and the partners' involvement.

Table 1. Audience overview.

Audience	Message to be communicated	Main impact	Partners involved
Owners of artefacts and/or databases	Raise awareness of the project. Stimulate interest in project technologies. Encourage to use and validate GRAVITATE outcomes.	National, European, International	The British Museum and the Cyprus Institute
The geometry processing community	The production of geometric data representations and conversions between them as well as the development of efficient algorithms which will propose possible matches can be exploited in different applications.	National, European, International	University of Amsterdam CNR-IMATI Technion
The semantic web community	New techniques incorporating semantic technologies may be proposed as a result of our work, and our results will be available to museums, libraries and archives to ensure that the descriptive metadata we develop and the novel tools to manipulate 3D representations permits effective integration between the different sources of cultural heritage information that are held and published by them.	National, European, International	The British Museum, Cyprus Institute, IT Innovation
Policy groups, agencies and governments	Demonstrate how European collaboration has achieved more than would have otherwise been possible, notably in achieving scientific excellence, contributing to competitiveness and solving societal challenges. Show how the outcomes are relevant to our everyday lives, by creating jobs, introducing novel technologies, or making our lives more comfortable in other ways.	National, European, International	All partners
Sister projects	Raise awareness of the project. Stimulate interest in project technologies. Develop synergies. Disseminate best practices and project results.	European	All partners, but mainly WP leaders
Science Journalists	Raise awareness of the project Stimulate interest in project content. Encourage to use and validate the project outcomes.	National, European, International	All partners

Audience	Message to be communicated	Main impact	Partners involved
Private sector	Raise awareness of the project. Cultivate interest in the deployment of specialized services to support extensions/customizations of the services of the GRAVITATE platform. Encourage to use and validate GRAVITATE outcomes.	National, European, International	IT innovation
General Public	Raise awareness of the project. Stimulate interest in project content. Encourage to use and validate GRAVITATE outcomes.	National, European, International	All partners

Action: All Partners to identify the relevant stakeholders in their existing networks and prepare a contact list for dissemination purposes.

3. Rationale for disseminating through a Website and Social Media channels

Project Website

A website can be used for raising awareness, building anticipation and disseminating project results. Below are some of benefits related to having a website dedicated to the project.

Cost Effectiveness

A strategically developed website and online presence solution provides tremendous benefits and costing outlines.

Accessibility around the clock

Website and social media accounts are accessible 24/7/365. Since the project website is operational around the clock, from a desktop, a tablet and a mobile phone the project's target groups can easily access it at the most convenient time and place for them.

Credibility

By building a website the project consortium has the opportunity to tell their target groups why the research project is important, the progress made and the opportunities that arise for them to join some of the project activities and benefit from the final results. When there is clarity and transparency regarding the project implementation positive word-of-mouth about the project is likely to spread. This in turn, contributes to an increase interest and anticipation for the final results.

Social Media Channels

Social Media channels are regarded by GRAVITATE's consortium as an essential part of the project's dissemination strategy. Social Media networking aims at creating content that attracts attention from a wide audience and encourages users to share it with their social networks.

On Social Media a message can be spread from user to user and as it is shared by a known/trusted source it is often accepted and shared further. Social networking sites allow individual followers to "retweet" or "repost" comments made by the project that is being promoted. By repeating the message, all user connections are able to see the message, therefore reaching more people. Social networking sites are the act of word-of-mouth model that is one of the most successful and oldest marketing models.

Some of the most popular Social Media channels such as Facebook, Twitter and YouTube were chosen for GRAVITATE's promotion in order to engage a wide audience.

In a nutshell, being active on the internet means that GRAVITATE will be easily reachable, easily understandable, interesting, almost everywhere and interconnected.

4. Website

GRAVITATE's Project Website: gravitate-project.eu

Date of creation: June 2015 (PM1)

Technical Characteristics

For the development of the technical characteristics of GRAVITATE's website we used Drupal 7 as a content management system. Drupal is an open source CMS with a large community of programmers and users. It is built on the PHP programming language and stores all its content on MySQL relational database.

Drupal offered flexibility that allowed us to customize different modules, making it easier to make updates. We were also attracted to the flexibility of Drupal's entity system, which allowed us to present content in different ways across the site, whether lists, text, audio, or images.

4.1. Home Page

The home page is regarded the most important page, since it will get more page views than any other one. It therefore features some critical elements such as a headline, the navigation bar etc. Social Media are highlighted. It also features the European Commission official logo.

GRAVITATE PROJECT REPRESENTATIVES AT BRITISH MUSEUM

Questionnaire : This questionnaire is a tool for guiding the information gathering from users in workshops and interviews.

About GRAVITATE

The overall objectives of the **GRAVITATE** project are to create a set of software tools that will allow archaeologists and curators to reconstruct shattered or broken cultural objects, to identify and re-unify parts of a cultural object that has been separated across collections and to recognise associations between cultural artefacts that will allow new knowledge and understanding of past societies to be inferred.

The project involves, as partners, a world-renowned museum, an archaeology institute, and research partners working in the manipulation of 3-D objects, semantic analysis and ICT integration. The project is driven by the needs of the archaeological institutes, exemplified by a pertinent use case, the Salamis collection shared between Cyprus and the British Museum.

Expertise in 3-D scanning from previous project experience enables the partners to embark on a programme of geometrical feature extraction and matching on the one hand, and semantic annotation and matching on the other. The integration of these approaches into a single decision support platform, with a full suite of visualisation tools will provide a unique resource for the cultural heritage research community.

keywords

- ✓ Semantic Mapping
- ✓ Geometric Matching
- ✓ 3D visualisation
- ✓ Metadata
- ✓ Museum Artifacts

4.2. Partners

This page has the list of all organisations that are part of the consortium. It contains a brief description of all partners, logos and a link for each partner website.

IT Innovation Centre

The IT Innovation Centre (www.it-innovation.soton.ac.uk) is an applied research centre advancing a wide range of information technologies and their deployment in industry, commerce and the public sector. Part of Electronics and Computer Science at the University of Southampton, the Centre is an international leader in applied research in secure service-oriented systems, information discovery and decision support, and archiving and retrieval, and their relationship to new business models, processes and values. We address technical challenges in conjunction with business, operational and societal challenges. We present the results of our work as software demonstrators, white papers, confidential reports and targeted academic and technical publications. Our substantial portfolio of collaborative research supported by public programmes is complemented by professional services including customer-specific and commercially confidential research and development, bespoke development of operational systems for early adopters, consultancy, and technology due diligence. We are currently working in sectors ranging from the creative industries to environment, finance, health and engineering. We work in a spirit of partnership, ensuring effective transfer of knowledge. We have a strong record of relevant collaborative research in UK and European programmes. We typically play a leading role, driving the development and integration of advanced solutions. We have a deep understanding of the different convergence perspectives of the Future Internet (content, services, security), are engaged with UK and European bodies regarding Future Internet policy and strategy, and active in the Future Internet Assembly. We are steering board members of the European Technology Platforms NESSI and NEM.

University of Amsterdam (UVA)

The University van Amsterdam (UvA) is the largest university in the Netherlands, a member of the League of European Research Universities (LERU), one of the top research universities in Europe and among the top 50 universities in the world (QS World University Rankings 2014). The Informatics Institute (IVI) (ivi.uva.nl) is one of the eight departments in the Faculty of Science. IVI is and has been involved in many national and EU funded projects, and collaborates with a large number of research groups, nationally and internationally. It aims at applying information technology to

4.3. News and Events

This page contains the latest news and events. It will be updated frequently by the dissemination WP leader with useful, accurate and actual information which will be provided by the consortium partners.

Date	Gravitate Events
Friday, October 2, 2015	WORKSHOP 85 "The Role of Similarity in the Re-unification, Re-assembly and Re-association of 3D Artefacts"
Monday, July 27, 2015	The role of similarity in the re-unification, re-assembly and re-association of 3D artefacts

4.4. Publications

This page will inform the community about all the work performed along the way, whether is a deliverable, a conference paper or scientific publications.

4.5. Mailing List

The newsletter issues will keep the target audience up to date with news and project results. A mailing list will be also created in order to send newsletters.

Mailing list

Email Address

First Name

Last Name

[Subscribe to list](#)

4.6. Contact Us

For further information about the project and for any questions the audience might have, the project provides the coordinator's contact details.

The screenshot shows the desktop version of the GRAVITATE website's contact page. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for 'Contact Us', 'Events', 'Partners', 'Mailing List', and 'Questionnaire'. The 'Contact Us' link is highlighted. Below the navigation, the page title is 'Contact' and the breadcrumb trail shows 'You are here: Home'. The main content area is divided into three columns:

- Our Location:** Features a Google Map of the IT Innovation Centre in Chilworth, Southampton. A pop-up window provides the address: 'IT Innovation Centre, Gamma House, Enterprise Road, Southampton SO16 7NS, United Kingdom'. It also includes 'Directions' and 'Save' buttons.
- Contact information:** Lists the address, phone number (+44 23 8059 8866), email (info@gravitate-project.eu), and website (www.it-innovation.soton.ac.uk/).
- Social Media:** Includes icons for Twitter and Facebook.

At the bottom, there is a 'Contact Form' with three input fields: 'Your name *', 'Your e-mail address *', and 'Subject *'.

4.7. Use on mobile devices

Since 2010 mobile searches have seen a 400% increase. A mobile-friendly site can thus help connect with the target audience.

The site is designed with mobile users in mind and adapts to fit well on small screens. It offers simple navigation capabilities and takes advantage of the natural mobile phone features such as maps, location information and click-to-call.

4.8. Monitoring

Google analytics is used to measure website usage. Usage data will be reviewed for the website over each year and around target events. If usage is not as good as expected, an investigation will be made as to why and improvements will be made where possible.

Website statistics will include:

- Number of unique visits per page (timestamped)
- Average time spent per visit per page
- Number of downloads (PDF, data, code, slides) (timestamped)

Actions:

- Partners will send all their relevant information and documentation to enrich the project website and to be shared by all.
- Partners are advised to include a page or a section describing the project's activities and results on their institutional website and link to the project site.
- **Partner institutions' websites:** partners are encouraged to disseminate GRAVITATE activities and outcomes on their own institutional websites, periodically updating news, and links to relevant documentation.
- **Online communication:** Partners are encouraged to promote GRAVITATE activities and outcomes on their institutional newsletters, e-bulletins and social media marketing tools.

5. Social Media Channels

The adoption of Social Networks profiles will allow the project to support viral visibility of the GRAVITATE website content and help spread online world word-of-mouth about the research progress and wealth of materials available.

5.1. Facebook

Facebook Page: <https://www.facebook.com/Gravitate-Project-1003877466341479/>

Target groups: people in our database list, press contacts, followers of the partners' Facebook pages, survey participants.

On every kind of website we can find the Facebook page or like button. That means Facebook plays two important roles: firstly it is used as a space where organisations can create their fan pages and on the other hand it's the way we start to measure successfulness of the project's popularity.

What does Facebook allow us to do?

- It provides an informative page with all the types of information on statuses, links, photos, posters, events, etc.;
- All the people in our GRAVITATE contacts database list should receive an invitation to join/like our GRAVITATE Facebook page;
- Every week the information on the GRAVITATE page should be updated to create traffic.

The Facebook page is only useful if the partnership manages to keep it alive by publishing regular posts about the project and other related topics. It is highly recommended that all partners contribute to the Facebook page on a regular basis by liking, commenting and above all promoting the page and inviting new people. The main communication language will be English but all partners can also use contributions in their national languages. Furthermore, each partner can create events for the promotion of national activities.

Action:

- Consortium members that use their professional/personal Facebook space should find a way to share information about GRAVITATE, by sending invitations to like the page and its posts to people in their contacts database list and in their networks.
- The Facebook page is currently administered by STARC-CyI only. However, one person per Consortium member can have access to the administration of the GRAVITATE Facebook page and thus be able to post and create events, also at national level.
- All project researchers are encouraged to follow the project's social media with their own social media accounts. This will allow partners to post about their work and then the project account to retweet and comment on it and vice versa.

5.2. Twitter

Twitter page: https://twitter.com/gravitate_eu

Target groups: followers of partners' Twitter pages, regional policy planners, stakeholders, EU level organisations

Twitter is the closest network to the concept of buzz. It is the constant posting system that rests on the idea of the short sentences and reactions that show the positive or negative attitudes of its users. Messages can link to the GRAVITATE website, Facebook profile, photos, videos, etc. This link provides followers the opportunity to spend more time interacting with GRAVITATE online.

A hashtag is a word or a phrase prefixed by the symbol #. GRAVITATE already exists as a hashtag. To gain new followers the main prospect is to use the hashtag by using the key words and phrases that are associated to the work done by GRAVITATE, the domain we are working in, the target groups we're addressing to.

Consortium members should sign-up to Twitter and follow GRAVITATE. Moreover, they are invited to retweet posts on GRAVITATE and address them to their own Twitter followers, and tweet on GRAVIATE associating the hashtag #GRAVITATE with other hashtags such as #3D reconstruction, etc.

The use relevant hashtags in the tweet is advised in order to be more easily picked up and the project's audience is broadened beyond the partners' followers.

The use of images (e.g. 4 images from PowerPoint presentations or posters at a conference) in a tweet is more attractive to a follower than a strapline.

When going on a project-related trip partners are encouraged to have a target of 2-4 trip report tweets, both on their work and other work of potential interest to the project's followers. This generates regular project twitter activity and provides information of value to followers. Partners can announce they will be on a trip beforehand so people have a chance to message them and arrange a face to face chat at the event.

Example tweet topics include:

- 1) Trip & demo announcements
- 2) Trip & demo reports
- 3) New content available
- 4) Related project being funded, kicking off, finishing with results, etc.

Actions:

- All project researchers are encouraged to follow the project's Social Media with their own social media accounts. This will allow partners to post about their work and then the project account to retweet and comment on it and vice versa.
- All the project social media accounts will be strictly professional and posts must have some information value otherwise followers unfollow GRAVITATE.

5.3. YouTube and SlideShare

YouTube is for uploading:

- Videos of events;

- Videos of interviews;
- Collage of pictures of relevant project milestones.

Often people will prefer to listen to a 5 minute video before they read a 5 page report.

Actions:

When using social media accounts (e.g. Twitter, YouTube, and Facebook) it is important to explicitly identify key influencers the project wants to attract as followers. At its start any project social media accounts will only have the project consortium as followers. If a key influencer starts to follow the account and retweet some of the projects work the extended range of these posts will increase by 2-3 orders of magnitude (i.e. key influencers can easily have 1,000's of followers each of which could be reading your retweeted post).

All partners are therefore encouraged to identify these key influencers and invite them. Furthermore, partners are encouraged to retweet some of the key influencer's work with the hope they follow the project's accounts.

Meeting such influencers face to face at events and giving a business card with social media account info is instrumental in the dissemination of the project.

If a key influencer does retweet a partner's tweet then retweeting is encouraged (i.e. magnify this evidence of impact).

All social media accounts should be active and partners should frequently provide input.

Social media statistics will include:

- 1) Number of followers and the 'extended range' of people you can reach if all followers retweeted (i.e. add up project followers + all their followers)
- 2) Number of target influencers following
- 3) Number of target influencer retweets
- 4) Number of retweets & downloads
- 5) Sentiment of the comments and retweets project is receiving

6. Action Plan

Here we summarise the action plan for the use of the website and social media channels which will target all relevant stakeholders.

Table 2. Action plan.

Activities	Frequency	Partner
GRAVITATE's website: publish posts on project updates	A least once every 2 months	CyI-STARC
GRAVITATE updates on partners' websites/network platforms/newsletters	Every 5-6 months	All partners
GRAVITATE's Facebook and Twitter: publicise events and opportunities of participation, share updates from the website, disseminate newsletters, laisse with stakeholders and contribute to raising awareness	At least once a month	CyI-STARC
GRAVITATE's YouTube and SlideShare: publicise videos and PowerPoint presentations from conferences, workshops etc.	Every 5-6 months	All partners
Sharing of information posted on GRAVITATE's social media and website through partners' social media	At least once every two months	All partners

7. Conclusion

This report documents the existence of the project's website and social media channels. The website was created in June 2015 and the Social Media channels soon after.

The document also describes the rationale for using the channels and summarises relevant aspects of the project's (internal) dissemination plan.